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LINGUISTIC BASIS OF PARALLEL CORPUS IN THE CREATION OF MT MODELS FOR UZBEK-ENGLISH LANGUAGES

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ANNOTATION

The article focuses on establishing linguistic support for machine translation through the development of a parallel corpus. It involves analyzing the materials gathered for the linguistic basis of the parallel corpus, evaluating a morphological translation dictionary that has been created, and the subsequent analysis of the outcomes.

Key words. Statistical Machine Translation, corpus-based MT, parallel corpus, linguistic bases of parallel corpus.

АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье основное внимание уделяется налаживанию лингвистического обеспечения машинного перевода посредством разработки параллельного корпуса. Он предполагает анализ собранных материалов для лингвистической основы параллельного корпуса, оценку созданного морфологического переводческого словаря и последующий анализ результатов.

Ключевые слова. Статистический машинный перевод, корпусный МП, параллельный корпус, лингвистические основы параллельного корпуса.

ANNOTATSIYA

Maqolada asosiy e'tibor mashina tarjimasining lingvistik ta'minoti sifatida parallel korpusni ishlab chiqishga qaratilgan. Bu parallel korpusning lingvistik asoslari uchun to'plangan materiallarni tahlil qilish, yaratilgan morfologik tarjima lug'atini izohlashni va erishilgan natijalarni tahlil qilishni o'z ichiga oladi.

Kalit so'zlar. Statistik mashina tarjimasi, korpusga asoslangan MT, parallel korpus, parallel korpusning lingvistik asoslari.

Introduction.

Machine translation is an automatic translation. This is the process of translating text from one natural language (English) to another (Uzbek) using computer software. Whether the translation is done manually or automatically, the content of the original (main) language text must be completely restored in the target language translation.

In world linguistics, many scientists have researched machine translation, N.D. Andriev, I.A. Melchuk, I.I. Revzin, V.Y. Rosensweig, Y.N. Marchuk, R.G. Piotrovsky, K.B. Bektayev, A.N. Belyayev, I.K. Belsky, A.V. Zubov, G.E. Miram, L.L. Nelyubin, V.I. Perebynos, V.A. Chijakovsky, Ye.A. Shingarev, G.G. Belonogov, R.G. Kotov, Babushkina N.V, Z. Shalyapina, O.Y. Mansurova, A.S. Panina, A.A. Khoroshilov (Russia); A. Booth, R. Richans, J. Hutchins, J. Allen, P. Brown

(USA); M. Nagao (Japan); A. Vaher (Estonia); J. Astrouni in France; R. Sinha, A. Jain (India); Among these are the works of researchers such as B. Blazer, U. Schwol, A. Storrer (Germany). In our republic, scientists such as A. Toshpolatov, M. Khakimov, M. Aripov, S. Muhamedov, Sh. Abidova, A. Akhmedova, N. Abdurakhmonova researched machine translation and language models, and corpus creation technologies. In particular, research conducted by N. Abdurakhmonova aimed at creating the linguistic support of a program that translates a text in a foreign language into Uzbek and vice versa. supply, several scientific works on corpus-based language teaching have been published.

Machine translation is one of the most complex areas of computational linguistics. Other specializations of linguistics that are cognitively, conceptually, and linguistically culturally demanding are considered when conducting research on natural languages. Translation is not only a technical process, but also a complex spiritual and scientific direction related to creative activity. Texts in colloquial and artistic style can have an extralinguistic influence on the meaning and integrity of the content. For this reason, we work with formal style texts in our research.

Method.

Our research is based on the "Statistics-based MT" type of "Corpus-based MT" and its linguistic support issues are highlighted. Statistical machine translation uses statistical translation models of parameters derived from the analysis of monolingual and bilingual corpus. Building a statistical translation model relies on an existing multilingual corpus. For a specific field, the corpus requires a lexicon of at least two million words, and for a general language, even more.

Results.

Due to the great demand for translation dictionaries to create an English-Uzbek translation environment, a bilingual morphological translation dictionary was created during our research. The units included in the dictionary were classified within word groups and their statistics were determined. Then, the most used phrases in the dictionary were nouns, verbs, and adjectives:

Picture 1

Parallel corpora are large collections of texts in two languages. They can be used in teaching and research in translation studies, machine translation, comparative studies, bilingual lexicography, and linguistics. Various opinions have been expressed by world scientists regarding the creation of parallel corpora. Alexander Rosen points out that creating parallel corpora, especially multilingual corpora, requires a large database because of the difficulty of matching the texts in the corpus.

Brown et al. [14; 89] were the first to use probability theory in machine translation. They create a probabilistic machine translation based on a parallel corpus of matched French-English texts. This system selects the most likely translation sentence in the target language from the source language sentence.

A parallel corpus provides translators with many alternatives and possibilities by searching for a corresponding source language element and extracting its terminological and lexical equivalent in the target language. It also allows you to find the most appropriate equivalent based on the context. This shows that parallel corpora are more important than simple bilingual dictionaries. Equivalents

from parallel corpora are completer and more accurate than those from bilingual dictionaries. The use of different types of corpora in lexicology is an effective way not only to create new dictionaries based on the corpus but also to improve the quality of existing ones.

To compile a bilingual dictionary, researchers try to automate the work due to the diversity of languages and the large amount of resources needed to create a dictionary. With the advent of statistical methods, great results have been achieved with less effort and resources. Because parallel corpus data are an invaluable source of bilingual data, they are widely used in statistical translation methods.

In terms of the importance of the parallel corpus, in our research, first of all, the Uzbek-English texts translated by professional translators were collected in excel state.

Analysis.

In our research, the parallel corpus contained in <http://uzbekcorpus.uz> was used. This corpus contains parallel texts in official, scientific, artistic styles in Uzbek-English, English-Uzbek, Russian-Uzbek, Uzbek-Russian, Turkish-Uzbek, Uzbek-Turkish and Korean-Uzbek, Uzbek-Korean languages. Our research object are English-Uzbek languages parallel texts in official style.

After collecting the database for the parallel corpus, the segmentation process is performed. The order of work performed within the framework of our research is as follows:

During the research, following the sequence of work, parallel texts in English and Uzbek languages in official style were collected for the linguistic support of the parallel corpus. In the process of checking the compatibility of sentences in English and Uzbek, some words found not to be expressed in the translation:

	C	D	E	F
1	Shavkat, Mirziyoyev, Shanghai, Cooperation, summit, take part in	Shavkat Mirziyoyev Shanxay hamkorlik tashkilotining navbatdagi sammitida ishtirok etdi 10.11.2020	Shavkat Mirziyoyev takes part in the Shanghai Cooperation Organization summit 10.11.2020	NOTE: navbatdagi so'zi tarjima qilinmaganligi uchun o'zbek til lug'atida bu so'z yozilmaydi.
2	President, Shavkat, Mirziyoyev, Shanghai, Cooperation, organization, state, head, council, videoconference, format, meeting, take part in	O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Shavkat Mirziyoyev 10-noyabr kuni Shanxay hamkorlik tashkilotiga a'zo davlatlar rahbarlari kengashining videoan'jumani shaklida o'tgan navbatdagi majlisida ishtirok etdi.	On November 10, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev took part in a regular meeting of Shanghai Cooperation Organization's Council of the Heads of State in videoconference format.	Note: O'zbekiston, Respublika, o'tgan, kun navbatdagi, a zoso'zlari tarjima qilinmagan
3	observer.nations.representative.Afghanistan.President, Ashraf, G'ani, Mongolia, President, Khaltmaagin, Battulga, Iran, President, Hasan, Rouhani, Belarus, Prime Minister, Roman, Golovchenko, also, SCO, general, secretary, Vladimir, Norov, and, SCO, regional, anti terrorism, structure, executive, committee, director, Jumalxon, Glyosov,	Bundan tashqari, sammit ishida SHHT huzuridagi kuzatuvchi davlatlar vakillari - Afg'oniston Islom Respublikasi Prezidenti Ashraf G'ani, Mo'g'uliston Prezidenti Xaltmaagiyin Battulga, Eron Islom Respublikasi Prezidenti Hasan Ruhoniy, Belarus Respublikasi Bosh vaziri Roman Golovchenko hamda SHHT Bosh kotibi Vladimir Norov va SHHT Mintaqaviy aksilterror tuzilmasi rahbarlari ishtirokida videokonferentsiya o'tkazildi.	representatives of SCO observer nations - President of Afghanistan Ashraf Ghani, President of Iran Hassan Rouhani, President of Mongolia Khaltmaagin Battulga, Prime Minister of Belarus Roman Golovchenko, as well as SCO Secretary-General Vladimir Norov and Director of the Executive Committee of the SCO Regional Anti-Terrorism Structure (RATS) Jumalxon Glyosov.	NOTE: islom, Respublika, ish, huzuridagi, qatnashdilar so'zlari tarjima qilinmagan
4	United, Nations, general, Secretary, Antonio, Guterres, summit, participant, videomurojaat, deliver	Birlashgan Millatlar Tashkiloti Bosh kotibi Antonio Gutierrez sammit ishtirokchilariga videomurojaat yo'lladi.	The United Nations Secretary-General Antonio Guterres delivered a video message to the summit participants.	NOTE: Tashkilot so'zining tarjimasi berilmagan
5	meeting, agenda, in accordance with, SCO, within, multifaceted, interaction, enhancement, spotlight	Uchrashuv kuni tartibiga muvofiq yangi global xabar va tahdidlarning kuchayishi sharoitida SHHT doirasidagi ko'p qirrali hamkorlikni yanada mustahkamlash masalalari muhokama qilindi.	In accordance with the agenda of the meeting, issues of enhancement of multifaceted interaction within the SCO were in spotlight.	Note: global, xabar, tahdidlar, sharoitida, so'zlarining tarjimasi berilmagan
6	delegations, head, priority, are, multi, lateral, relation, current, state, analyze, prospect, and, also, international, and, regional, pressing, affair, exchange view	taslimotga a'zo va kuzatuvchi maqomidagi davlatlar delegatsiyalarining rahbarlari ustuvor yo'nalishlarda ko'p tomonlama munosabatlarning bugungi holatini tahlil qilib, ularni rivojlantirish istiqbollari muhokama qilindi, shuningdek, xalqaro va mintaqaviy ahamiyatga molik dolzarb masalalar yuzasidan fikr almashdilar.	The heads of delegations analyzed the current state and prospects of multilateral relations in priority areas, and also exchanged views on pressing regional and international affairs.	NOTE: tashkilot, a'zo, va, kuzatuvchi, maqomidagi, ul, (afsona) rivojlantirish, muhok, qililar, dolzarb, yuzasidan

Picture 2

For the parallel corpus, we took 400 sentence components translated from Uzbek to English from <http://prezident.uz>, and the collected materials were placed in the parallel corpus database created at <http://uzbekcorpus.uz>:

Picture 3

One of the problems in automatic translation is that lexemes acquire polysemantic meaning. It is known that polysemy is a variety, and semantically they are related to each other. For example, while the lexeme “head” in the Uzbek language represents the upper part of the body, keeping this meaning, it is also used with several other words, for example, the beginning of the street, the beginning of the work, the beginning of the word, etc.

In the Uzbek language, a polysemantic word is observed within only one word group, while in English, it may belong to a different group in terms of meaning proximity. For example, [1]

Noun	Adjective	Verb	Translation
Act		Act	xatti-harakat (qilmoq)
Anger		Anger	jahl (chiqmoq)
	approximate	Approximate	taxminiy (taxmin qilmoq)
Attack		Attack	hujum (qilmoq)
Base		Base	asos (solmoq)
	Calm	Calm	tinch (-imoq)
Care		Care	diqqat (qaratmoq)
Challenge		Challenge	qiyinchilik; chaqirmoq
Chemical	Chemical		kimyoviy modda; kimyoviy
Circle		Circle	aylana; atrofida aylanmoq
	clean	Clean	toza (-lamoq)
Close	Close	Close	yakun; yaqin; berkitmoq

The phenomenon of polysemy in English is relatively well studied. However, all of the words selected for automatic translation should be included in the full linguistic support and their features should be revealed in the Uzbek translation.

Homonymy is an important aspect of the translation process, because during analysis - in morpho analysis, it is necessary to determine whether a word is a noun or a verb. At the center of semantic problems in machine translation is the phenomenon of homonymy at the linguistic level in the text. The bilingual morphological dictionary created for linguistic support also contains

homonyms, and we analyzed in Excel how many of them form homonyms within a word group and determined the statistics:

Названия строк	Общий ит...	Nechta turkumli...	ADJ	ADJ/ADV	ADI/NOI	ADV	ADV/Prepositi...	Article	Conjunction	Conjunction/Prepositi...	Determinati...
4 round	5	4				2					
6 like	4	4		1							
7 one	4	4		1		1					
8 rough	4	4		1		1					
9 sixteen	4	4				1					
10 third	4	4				1					1
11 right	5	3		2		2					
12 second	5	3									1
13 outside	4	3		1		2					
14 top	4	3		1							
15 limp	3	3		1							
16 mass	3	3		1							
17 mine	3	3									
18 minus	3	3		1							
19 monthly	3	3		1		1					
20 near	3	3		1				1			
21 nineteenth	3	3				1					1
22 ninth	3	3				1					1
23 no	3	3									
24 north	3	3		1		1					
25 north-east	3	3		1		1					
26 north-west	3	3		1		1					
27 okav	3	3			1						

Picture 4

Conclusion.

In short, the parallel corpus consists of original and translated texts, and it allows to determine the methods used by the translator and conduct various translation studies. Parallel corpora for automatic translation can be used to generate typical translation methods and transformations, to study automatic translation system statistics, to create monolingual and multilingual dictionaries, and to automatically check the accuracy of translations. Also, to facilitate the translator's work through the wide range of equivalent options.

In the parallel corpus, along with scientific and official style, parallel examples of artistic and popular style, which are relatively difficult to translate, can be collected. Through this, it is possible to achieve the correct translation of texts in artistic and popular style.

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7 ЖИЛД, 3 СОН

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